

The Relationship between Conceptual Organizational Culture and the Level of Tolerance in Employees

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Abstract—The aim of the present study is examining the relationship between conceptual organizational culture and the level of tolerance in employees of Islamic Azad University of Shahre Ghods. This research is a correlational and analytic-descriptive one. The samples included 144 individuals. A 24-item standard questionnaire of organizational culture by Cameron and Queen was used in this study. This questionnaire has six criteria and each criterion includes four items that each item indicates one cultural dimension. Reliability coefficient of this questionnaire was normed using Cronbach's alpha of 0.91. Also, the 25-item questionnaire of tolerance by Conroy and Davidson was used. This questionnaire is in a five-degree Likert scale form. It has seven criteria and is designed to measure the power of coping with pressure and threat. It has the needed content reliability and its reliability coefficient is normed using Cronbach's alpha of 0.87. Data were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient and multivariable regression. The results showed among various dimensions of organizational culture, there is a positive significant relationship between three dimensions (family, adhocracy, bureaucracy) and tolerance, there is a negative significant relationship between dimension of market and tolerance and components of organizational culture have the power of prediction and explaining the tolerance. In this explanation, the component of family is the most effective and the best predictor of tolerance.

Keywords—Adhocracy, bureaucracy, organizational culture, tolerance.

I. INTRODUCTION

TODAY'S world is changing socially, economically and politically. If organizations, as the main basis of the society and as its subsystem, want to continue existing, they should be able to adapt themselves with environmental changes. Surely, there are some individuals in these organizations that work together each of them having different personality and interests. These individuals are of the most important asset of an organization; the more these individuals of pleasant quality, the more the possibility of survival, success and progress of an organization. When these people get together, they create a collection of reactions, beliefs, values and norms among themselves that affect their behavior. Such a collection among a group of people is called, the culture of that group. This culture has a significant effect on organizations and in other words, it has become institutionalized within the organization.

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One of the most important internal factors of an organization is the culture and environment of an organization that is of special importance. If the organization is weak in factors such as culture and environment, surely it cannot reach a pleasant level. History shows that success in the performance of each organization is affected by organizational culture significantly. Some fundamental changes are happening in the attitude of some psychologists. The focus and the new direction of this attitude is called psychology of perfection or psychology of health that deals with the healthy aspect of the human, and not the unhealthy aspects. This new approach is called positive psychology [1]. The approach of positive psychology is attended by psychologists considering the talents and abilities of humans and not their abnormalities and disorders. The ultimate goal of this approach is identifying the structures and methods that bring about well-being and happiness for humans, which are the most fundamental structure that are studied in this approach. Humans have a special and unique capacity, as well as flexibility, despite their vulnerability and limitations [2].

Researchers believe that tolerance is not an individual concept, but is a collection of abilities such as social competence, communication skills, problem-solving skills, sense of purpose and sense of competence [3]. Generally, the organizational culture is an understanding that individuals have of their organization; it is something that exists in organization and not in the individual. Special characteristics that exist in an organization indicate usual and fixed characteristics that differentiate organizations from each other [4]. Considering that organizational culture is the system of values, beliefs and common customs among members of organization and develops the interaction of different parts, therefore, it is considered as an effective tool in increasing the level of tolerance in employees of organization. Researches show the low level of tolerance in an organization is resulted from the lack of organizational culture and not understanding it. Organizational culture affects the behaviors and thoughts of members of organization as a collection of common beliefs and values and it can be considered as a beginning point for movement and dynamism, and an obstacle in development of an organization [5].

In the present study, organization, as well as culture, is considered as a cultural phenomenon that characteristics of culture are explored in it. Culture of each organization is a miniature of the culture of society but it is not exactly the culture of the society. The culture of an organization can be seen in the structure, rules, policies, goals, and the explanation of the jobs and the way of undertaking its missions, but it is

the human element that gives soul to it and actually creates it. The main mission of the educational systems, especially universities, is for training the human resources necessary for this development. The main issue that is examined in the present study is whether there is a relationship between hardiness and tolerance with organizational culture or not. Therefore, considering the key role of the university as the most important scientific basis of growing a skilled, aware and experienced employee, conducting this research is important for two reasons. The first one is that the researcher aims to identify the level of the relationship between organizational culture with the tolerance among employees of Islamic Azad University of Shahre Ghods. The second one is that the researcher attempts to give some recommendations in order to identify organizational culture and increasing the level of tolerance to employees. Considering what is presented, the researcher aims to examine the relationship between organizational culture with the level of tolerance among employees of Islamic Azad University of Shahre Ghods.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Since, the present study aims to examine the relationship between perceived organizational culture with the level of tolerance among employees of Islamic Azad University of Shahre Ghods. The method is descriptive and correlational. All 230 employees of Islamic Azad university of Shahre Ghods consist the statistical population of the study. Among them, 144 individuals were selected by simple random sampling method using Morgan Table.

III. TOOLS

Organizational Culture Questionnaire: This questionnaire is designed and set by Cameron and Queen [6] in the field of organizational culture in order to measure the culture dimensions of the organization. This questionnaire has six criteria, each with four items (A, B, C, D). Each of these four items represents one cultural dimension, which are:

1. Family culture dimension,
2. Adhocracy culture dimension,
3. Market culture dimension, and
4. Bureaucratic culture dimension.

The questions will be answered in the existence condition of the organization. The existence condition is that which exists in the organization.

Items one to four are related to the significant organizational characteristics, items four to eight are related to the organizational leadership, items eight to 12 are related to the management of employees, items 12 to 16 are related to the organizational linking, items 12 to 16 are related to the strategic focuses and items 20 to 24 are related to the criteria of success.

The total sum of the score in each criterion at maximum level is 100, which is divided into four items based on the comment of the responders. This questionnaire has been applied in various studies. The reliability coefficient of this tool was normed using Cronbach's alpha that was 0.91.

Tolerance Questionnaire: This questionnaire is made by Conor and Davidson [7], through reviewing research resources in the field of tolerance, in order to measure the power of coping pressure and threats. The designer of this questionnaire believes that this scale can separate individuals with tolerance in clinical and nonclinical groups well. This questionnaire has seven components that has 25 items with a 5-degree Likert scale that is scored from Totally incorrect (zero) to Totally correct (100). The maximum score in this questionnaire is 100 and the minimum score is 0. The score of each subject equals to the sum of scores or the total values obtained from each item. The level of tolerance of each subject equals to the obtained raw score divided by 100 and multiplied by 100.

The reliability of the tool: The total reliability of the questionnaire using Cronbach's alpha was 0.91 for organizational culture and 0.89 for tolerance.

IV. FINDING

Descriptive data including gender, age, education and the history of work were studied in this study and were considered in analyzing the issues. Men make up the largest group in the sample, consisting of 84 individuals (58%) of the sample, while the remainder of the sample group consists of 60 women (42%).

Participants with a B.A. degree consists of 86 individuals or 60% of the sample, while those with a diploma represent the smallest number of the sample of 19 individuals, representing 13% of the sample.

Individuals with a working history of 5 years to 7 years make up the largest group in the sample with 79 individuals or 55%, while those with a 10-year working history make up the lowest number of nine individuals, representing 6%.

The findings show that 25 year to 30 year olds represented the largest group in the sample consisting of 59 individuals, or 41%, while 43 year to 47 year olds represented the lowest number of the sample, consisting of 12 individuals or 8%.

TABLE I
 CHARACTERISTICS OF DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE STUDIED VARIABLES
 (N=144)

Variables	standard deviation	Mean
Tolerance	15.142	34.47
Family Culture	85.201	152.80
Adhocracy culture	59.281	132.99
Market Culture	73.225	155.47
Democratic culture	84.930	171.82

As it can be seen in Table I, the mean of the dependent variable of tolerance was 34.47 and its standard deviation was 15.142. Among the independent variables, the highest mean was related to dimension of democratic culture, which was 171.82 and a standard deviation of 84.930, while the lowest mean was related to the dimension of adhocracy culture that is 132.99 and a standard deviation of 59.281.

To identify the best predictor of tolerance among predicting variables, regression model with simultaneous method and

partial correlation were used. The results are presented in Table II.

The findings of the study showed calculated correlation coefficient was significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ ($r = 0.570$, $P = 0.000$). They indicate that there is a significant relationship between variables of organizational culture with tolerance in employees. In other words, the more the organizational culture, the higher the tolerance of the employees, other than the component of organizational culture of market that the

more the organizational culture, the less the tolerance in employees.

TABLE II
CORRELATION COEFFICIENT OF VARIABLES OF TOLERANCE WITH COMPONENTS OF PREDICTING VARIABLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

Variables	r	p
Family Culture	0.413**	0.000
adhocracy culture	0.274**	0.000
Market Culture	0.213**	0.005
democratic culture	0.140*	0.047

0.01 < *; 0.05 < *P

TABLE III
MULTIPLE CORRELATION COEFFICIENT AND SQUARE OF MULTIPLE CORRELATION OF COMPONENTS OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN PREDICTING THE TOLERANCE

Criterion variable	Prediction variable	Level of significance	Coefficient of F	Square of multiple adjusted correlation coefficient	Square of multiple correlation coefficient	Multiple correlation coefficient
Tolerance	Bureaucratic culture Adhocracy Culture Family Culture Market Culture	0.000	16.614	0.305	0.325	0.570

Based on the findings of Table III, the relationship between bureaucratic culture, adhocracy culture, family culture and the culture of market is significant in predicting the tolerance in employees ($F = (4, 168) = 67.418$, $p = 0.000$).

The results are presented in Table IV to identify the coefficients of regression analysis and significant predicting power for independent variables and adjusting regression equation.

TABLE IV
STANDARD AND NONSTANDARD REGRESSION ANALYSIS COEFFICIENTS FOR PREDICTING TOLERANCE

Criterion variable	Statistical index of predicting variable	Beta nonstandard coefficients	t	Beta standard coefficient	Standard error	Level of significance
Tolerance	constant number	0.067	1.849-		8.123	15.09-
	Family Culture	0.000	6.744	0.607	0.016	0.108
	Adhocracy culture	0.000	4.063	0.322	0.020	0.082
	Market Culture	0.002	3.203	0.320	0.021	0.062
	Bureaucratic culture	0.000	4.671	0.385	0.015	0.069

Considering the results of Table IV and significance of F in Table of variance analysis and t in the Table IV regression equation is related to all predictors of the organizational culture significantly.

The indices presented in Table V show the partial ability of each predictor.

TABLE V
DUAL AND PARTIAL VARIABLE CORRELATIONS OF PREDICTORS WITH EFFECT ON TOLERANCE

Correlation of dual variables	Partial correlations	Variable
Family Culture	0.498**	0.413**
Adhocracy culture	0.327**	0.274**
Market Culture	0.263**	0.213**
Bureaucratic culture	0.370**	0.140*

Correlation of dual variables: correlation of each predictor and tolerance

Partial correlations: correlation of each predictor and tolerance with controlling other predictors

$P^{**} < 0.1$, $P^* < 0.05$

As it can be seen, in dual-variable correlations, there is a positive and significant relationship between all values of tolerance and four components of organizational culture ($p < 0.01$) and among partial correlations also all values of

tolerance and four components of organizational culture are significant ($p < 0.01$). Based on this correlational analysis, it can be concluded that the family culture dimension is a more useful predictor that by its own predicts 17% (r^2) of the changes of tolerance. It is while the proportion of the other variables are just 15%. Based on the data of Table V, the research hypotheses are examined.

The main hypothesis: There is a relationship between organizational culture and tolerance in employees.

Based on the data of the research, the calculated correlation coefficient is significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ ($p = 0.000$ and $r = 0.570$). It indicates that there is a positive and significant relationship between the variables of organizational culture with tolerance in employees. In other words, the more the organizational culture, the more the tolerance in employees.

The first hypothesis: There is a relationship between family culture and tolerance in employees.

Based on the data of the research, the calculated correlation coefficient between the component of family culture dimension with tolerance is positive and significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ ($r = 0.413$, $p = 0.000$). In other words, the more the family culture, the more the tolerance in them.

Fig. 1 Correlation between variables of family culture dimension and tolerance

The second hypothesis: There is a relationship between adhocracy and tolerance among employees.

Based on the data of the research, the calculated correlation coefficient between the component of adhocracy culture of employee and tolerance is positive and significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ ($r = 0.274$, $p = 0.000$). In other words, the more the dimension of adhocracy culture in employees, the more tolerance in them.

Fig. 2 Correlation between the variables of dimension of adhocracy culture and tolerance

The third hypothesis: There is a relationship between culture of market and tolerance.

Based on the data of the research, the calculated correlation coefficient between the component of culture of market of employee and tolerance is negative and significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ ($r = -0.213$, $p = 0.005$). In other words, the more the dimension of culture of market in employees, the less tolerance in them.

The fourth hypothesis: There is a relationship between culture of bureaucratic and tolerance among employees.

Based on the data of the research, the calculated correlation coefficient between the component of bureaucratic culture of employee and tolerance is positive and significant at the level of $P < 0.01$ ($r = 0.14$, $p = 0.047$). In other words, the more the dimension of bureaucratic culture in employees, the more tolerance in them.

Fig. 3 Correlation between variables of bureaucratic culture and tolerance

V. CONCLUSION

The findings showed there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational culture and tolerance. In fact, employees who have high tolerance, have an important role in growing and prospering the organizational culture. In other words, employees with high tolerance are the essential requirements for promoting each organization. It means that the higher the tolerance in individuals, the higher the promotion of organizational culture in the organization. It needs using strong organizational culture in family, adhocracy, market and bureaucratic dimensions that can provide a friendly environment full of understanding and mutual trust in order for employees have improved mental health and increased spirit, and feel satisfied and secured. This is a basis to comprehend the understanding of organizational culture in organization.

The findings showed the calculated correlation coefficient between family component of employee and tolerance is positive and significant. In other words, the more the family component of organizational culture in employees, the more tolerance in them. In fact, it is because employees with high tolerance consider the organization as a personal and family environment in which individuals share, facilitate and grow the data. Employees with high tolerance think expanding humane resources needs high trust, openness and cooperation and always insist on loyalty, mutual trust and organizational commitment. They believe that progress and expansion is the result of team work, coming together, cooperation and interests of individuals.

The findings of the research showed the calculated correlation coefficient between the component of adhocracy culture of employee and tolerance is positive and significant. In other words, the more the dimension of adhocracy culture in employees, the more tolerance in them. In fact, it is because employees with high tolerance consider the organization as a dynamic entrepreneurial environment in which individuals tend to taking risks, entrepreneurship and innovation. Employees with high tolerance believe that the connection of the members of the organization requires commitment to innovation and expansion and always insist on achieving new resources, creating challenges and finding new and unique opportunities in organization.

The also findings showed the calculated correlation coefficient between component of market and tolerance in employees is negative and significant. In other words, the higher the organizational culture, the lower the tolerance. In fact, it is because employees with high tolerance believe that organizational environment is result-oriented and members of the organization are success-oriented and competitive. It results in severe competition and identifying success-seeking individuals with high needs in case of logical, aggressive and result-oriented models. Employees with high tolerance believe in competition and always insist on competition and achieving leading goals and success in the market.

The findings showed calculated the correlation coefficient between bureaucratic component and tolerance in employees is positive and significant. In other words, the higher the bureaucratic component of organizational culture, the more the tolerance. In fact, it is because employees with high tolerance believe that the organization is a complete structured and control-oriented place in which individuals work with coordination, organizing and high efficiency. Employees with high tolerance respect the rules and organizational policies with the aim of creating safety of employment, comfort and predictable relationships in an organization. They define success as based on the efficiency and always insist on performance, stability, efficiency, control and ease, and without troubled operations.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the independent variable of organizational culture (family, adhocracy, market and bureaucratic) can predict the criterion variable (tolerance).

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